

Efficient Public Key Cryptosystem for wireless Network

Srinath Venkatesan

sv778@nyu.edu

New York university

ORCID:0000-0002-6845-627X

Sandeep Bhatnagar

Sandeep@wellsfargo.com

Wells Fargo Bank

Iván Mesias Hidalgo Cajo

ihidalgo@esPOCH.edu.ec

Escuela Superior Politécnica de Chimborazo – ESPOCH

ORCID: 0000-0002-9059-0272

Xavier Leopoldo Gracia Cervantes

xavier.gracia.cervantes@utelvt.edu.ec

Universidad Técnica Luis Vargas Torres

ORCID: 0000-0003-4962-583X

600

Abstract

Remote sensor networks comprise of self-ruling sensor hubs connected to at least one base stations. As Wireless sensor networks keeps on developing, they become defenseless against assaults and henceforth the requirement for viable security components. Public Key Cryptography (PKC) has been the empowering innovation fundamental numerous security administrations and conventions in customary organizations, for example, the Internet. The proposed approach presents a novel public key cryptosystem through which the cryptographic keys are created, put away and utilized in a safer way. The wellbeing investigation of the proposed approach is built up on twofold conjugacy over arithmetical structure and the outcomes express that it is profoundly secure and safe against picked ciphertext assault and beast power assault.

DOI Number: 10.48047/nq.2023.21.5.NQ222053

NeuroQuantology 2023;21(5):600-606

1. Introduction

The accessibility of modest radio handsets has empowered new sorts of uses and made new exploration challenges. Applications run from remote sensor organizations (WSNs) that can be utilized for wellbeing checking, mechanical control, and building robotization to keen cards that empower consistent client

confirmation and marking of computerized records. Contingent upon the application, these gadgets may trade data locally with peers, yet additionally worldwide with substances on the Internet. They are regularly conveyed in enormous amounts and in conditions where they might be presented to altering, listening in, and endeavors to adjust

sent information and addition unapproved messages into the organization. To counter such dangers, adaptable and compelling components for secure correspondence are basic. For some applications and gadgets viable, vitality is a basic and restricted asset. To survey the vitality requests of public-key cryptography, we measure the vitality cost¹ of streamlined programming usage of public-key calculations. Since the genuine advantages and exact examination of a specific calculation is intently attached to how it is utilized inside a security convention, we likewise consider conventions that give single-party and common verification. Furthermore, we consider the effect of public-key cryptography on battery life and contrast public-key cryptography with different elements affecting vitality utilization, for example, inactive tuning in, information gathering and transmission, symmetric cryptography, and so on. Our investigation can be summed up to assess the expense of public-key cryptography in other security conventions and applications with changing qualities.

The enormous developments of PC and correspondence frameworks lead to the improvement of the new age of cutting edge cryptosystems. By and large, "PKC" moreover named topsy-turvy framework makes use for two unique keys, for example, public key and private keys for trade methodology. The public keys are dispersed athwart conspire people saved secret. The realities deciphered by the "PKC" method canister remain unscrambled utilizing the proper private key. All in all, the information to be shared over a channel is interpreted by a public key and a beneficiary decodes the deciphered documents using their private key. In this manner, through a technique of the public key encryption measure, just the approved clients might unscramble the information [1, 2]. In contrast with "PKC" encryption frameworks is needs higher calculation with the end goal that this technique is hard to be applied over the enormous volume of the information [3]. A diagram of a "PKC" is given in figure 1.

601

The two significant downsides in existing public key cryptosystems are the foundation of a safe correspondence channel and key administration measures [13]. Further, unbalanced cryptographic frameworks are exceptionally costly and require more calculation assets for usage. An encryption plot with public key cryptosystem needs to satisfy a few prerequisites. Among them, a protected and security saving key trade measure assume a transcendent job. In this manner, in vogue these exertion, we existing a protected and upgraded "PKC" by close ring. The recommended technique is very helpless and gives a productive answer for twofold conjugacy issue over close ring. Further, it

forestalls picked ciphertext assault and savage power assault across open key encryption strategies.

2. Proposed Public key cryptostem for Wireless Network

2.1 USER INTERFACE DESIGN WIRELESS NETWORK

To cooperate to the client worker username is required for riddle text that no one yet ready for relating on servers(Refer Fig 2.1). On the off chance that the client beginning at now exits direct can login into the worker else client should choose Username, key and Email id to worker. Worker will share the whole client to move and depict the information.

Fig 2.1 USER INTERFACE DESIGN WIRLESS NETWORK

2.2 ORDER PROCESS WIRLESS NETWORK

Right when you login there is book list page. What the book you like and alright with cost in like way proposes click purchase now. s(Refer Fig 2.2) After you need to buy the book encased with the title ought to be bought and click make divide choice it will go for bank login page.

Blum prime of the arrangement $q = 7k + 1$. Alice arbitrarily selects the private key $i, j \in Z$ such that $1 \leq i \leq q - 1$ and $2 \leq j \leq q - 1$ then calculate $\eta = l^i m^j l^{-i} \pmod q$ and distributes her public key (η, l, m, q) .

Encryption:

Given a message $m \in N$ and Alice's public key (η, l, m, q) . Bob chooses randomly $p, q \in Z$ such that $1 \leq p \leq q - 1$ and $2 \leq q \leq q - 1$ then calculates $\rho_1 = e^p f^q e^{-p} \pmod q$, $\rho_2 = m \cdot e^p \eta^s e^{-p} \pmod q$ and to finish harvests the ciphertext (ρ_1, ρ_2) .

Decryption:

On received of the ciphertext (C_1, C_2) Alice performs the decryption of ciphertext by her private key:

$$\left[\rho_2 \left(e^l \rho_1^m e^{-l} \right)^{-1} \right] (\text{mod } q) = m$$

Correctness:

Correctness of the scheme is verified as follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\rho_2 \left(e^l \rho_1^m e^{-l} \right)^{-1} \right] (\text{mod } q) \\ & \left[m \cdot e^p \eta^s e^{-p} \left(e^l \rho_1^m e^{-l} \right)^{-1} \right] (\text{mod } q) \\ & \left[m \cdot e^p \eta^s e^{-p} \left(e^l \left(e^p f^q e^{-p} \right)^m e^{-l} \right)^{-1} \right] (\text{mod } q) \\ & = m \end{aligned}$$

3. Security Analysis

Chosen ciphertext attack

In the proposed approach, the value of decrypting the ciphertexts $\rho_1 = e^p f^q e^{-p} (\text{mod } q)$, into the plain text m is comparable toward perceptive $\left[m \cdot e^p \eta^s e^{-p} \left(e^l \left(e^p f^q e^{-p} \right)^m e^{-l} \right)^{-1} \right] (\text{mod } q)$. The adversary randomly select a message $\bar{m} \in N$ and calculates $\bar{m} \rho_2$ formerly forwards it toward Alice aimed at decryption process. Formerly, Alice calculates $\bar{m} \rho_2 \left(e^l \rho_1^m e^{-l} \right)^{-1}$. Such that, the opponent can recuperate the message m uncertainty he acquires $\bar{m} m$.

Brute force attack

An enemy who knows public parameters such as public key $\eta = l^i m^j l^{-i} (\text{mod } q)$ makes an attempt to find the key values in Z_*^q . In such case, if the refuge restrictions are larger than double near-ring conjugacy then it is difficult to disruption the near-ring. Trendy order to break the secret key using "Brute force attacks" $l, m \in Z$ it requires 2^{32} attempts.

Key recovers attacks

The proposal, the public key is defined as $\eta = l^i m^j l^{-i} (\text{mod } q)$. If the opponent knows $p \in Z$ he can try to recover a conjugator Z_*^p . If we select a suitably huge leading p over Z_*^q it is comparable to decipher "CSP" above Z_*^q . The other probable scenario if the opponent distinguishes $p \in Z$ formerly he can resolve DLP over Z_*^q .

4. Result and Discussion

He expense of a public-key security convention can be separated into computational expense and correspondence cost. The measure of energy spent can be limited by picking the best algorithm(s), lessening the correspondence overhead of the security convention, and restricting the quantity of validation and key trade handshakes. An organization comprising of fixed hubs will likely expect handshakes to trade mystery keys at organization time; symmetric encryption can be utilized from that point. In these cases, an interest based confirmation plan might be more fitting. For instance, a hub may find its neighbors, yet play out a handshake just when it has private information to send/get or in any case stay torpid.

Scheme	Un-traceability	Perfect forward	Two-factor security	Mutual authentication
McEliece et al[2]	Yes	No	Yes	No
Bresson et al[3]	No	Yes	No	No
Cramer et al[4]	No	No	No	Yes
Steiner et al[6]	No	No	Yes	Yes
Our Scheme	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Security Comparison of Proposed Scheme

604

Scheme	User	Authentication Server	Total Time
McEliece et al[2]	$4m+2e+5s$	$4m+2e+2s$	$8m+4e+7s$
Bresson et al[3]	$3m+2e+5s$	$5m+5e+5s$	$8m+4e+10s$
Cramer et al[4]	$6m+2e+4s$	$4m+2e+2s$	$10m+4e+6s$
Our Scheme	$2m+4e+4s$	$6m+2e+2s$	$8m+6e+6s$

Computational Cost Analysis

Communication Analysis

5. Conclusion

Remote sensor networks proceed to develop and turn out to be broadly utilized in numerous applications. Thus, the requirement for security gets crucial. Be that as it may, the remote sensor network experiences numerous requirements, for example, restricted vitality, handling ability, and capacity limit, and so forth. The proposed approach presents a protected and proficient strategy of PKC by close ring. It chips away at the premise of twofold conjugacy issue. From the investigation it is seen that the dynamic execution of non-commutative close ring in proposed approach empowers secure remote sensor organization and the board cycle. Along these lines, the proposed strategy is incredibly productive and it is cryptographically difficult to break.

References

1. ElGamal, T., 1985. A public key cryptosystem and a signature scheme based on discrete logarithms. *IEEE transactions on information theory*, 31(4), pp.469-472.
2. McEliece, R.J., 1978. A public-key cryptosystem based on algebraic. *Coding Thv*, 4244, pp.114-116.
3. Cramer, R. and Shoup, V., 1998, August. A practical public key cryptosystem provably secure against adaptive chosen ciphertext attack. In *Annual International Cryptology Conference* (pp. 13-25). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
4. Steiner, M., Tsudik, G. and Waidner, M., 1996. Diffie-Hellman key distribution extended to group communication.
5. Bresson, E., Chevassut, O., Pointcheval, D. and Quisquater, J.J., 2001, November.

- Provably authenticated group Diffie-Hellman key exchange. In *Proceedings of the 8th ACM conference on Computer and Communications Security* (pp. 255-264). ACM.
6. V. MUTHUKUMARAN, D. EZHILMARAN: *Authenticated Group Key Agreement Protocol Based on Twisted Conjugacy Root Extraction Problem in Near-Ring*, Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience., **15**(6-7) (2018), 2023–2026.
 7. V. MUTHUKUMARAN, D. EZHILMARAN, G. S. G. N. ANJANEYULU: *Efficient Authentication Scheme Based on the Twisted Near-Ring Root Extraction Problem*, Advances in Algebra and Analysis, **5** (2018), 37–42.
 8. D. EZHILMARAN, V. MUTHUKUMARAN: *Key Exchange Protocol Using Decomposition Problem In Near-Ring*, Advances in Algebra and Analysis, **29**(1) (2016), 123–127.
 9. D. Ezhilmaran, V. Muthukumar: *Authenticated group key agreement protocol based on twist conjugacy problem in near-rings*, Wuhan University Journal of Natural Sciences, **22**(6) (2017), 472–476.
 10. V. Muthukumar, D. Ezhilmaran: *Efficient authentication scheme based on nearing root extraction problem*, Materials Science and Engineering Conference Series, **15** (2017), 042137.
 11. V. MUTHUKUMARAN, D. EZHILMARAN, I. MUCHTADI-ALAMSYAH, R. UDHAYAKUMAR, A. MANICKAM: *New public key cryptosystem based on combination of NREP and CSP in non-commutative near-ring*, Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology, **12**(3) (2020), 4534–4539.

